

Prof. Dr. Carlos De Marqui Junior
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Dear Prof. Carlos De Marqui Junior, coordinator of the ENVIBRO Project,

I am pleased to express my interest in the available post-doctoral fellowship within the ENVIBRO project. My Bachelor's degree in Mechanical Engineering was awarded by UNESP, Ilha Solteira, and I am currently pursuing a PhD degree at the same campus with its defense scheduled for January 2025.

My undergraduate trajectory included 28 months of research granted by FAPESP and the best student distinctions in my program. The undergraduate research supported me in accomplishing experience in powerful mathematical Lie symmetry methods and applying them to solve differential equations from structural mechanics and vibration.

The focus of my PhD research, granted by FAPESP, is on providing exact solutions to vibration models of continuous structures with nonuniform designs made of functionally graded materials using symmetry methods. We have found original exact solutions for classes of differential equations in terms of mode shapes and traveling waves for comprehensive geometric and material structural parameters, aiming at reaching closer to the ones seen in simple metamaterials.

My international research experiences include a BEPE/FAPESP internship during my undergraduate research in France, supervised by Prof. Jean-Mathieu Mencik, and a research internship granted by AUIP in Spain, supervised by Prof. Adrián Ruiz, studying analytical mode shape expressions for continuous structures and solving techniques for nonlinear modeling partial differential equation for wave propagation phenomena, respectively.

The invariant-based transformations from symmetry methods are manifold deformations, according to the ones from topology that preserve topological indexes invariant. Meanwhile, working with metamaterials represents a continuation of ideas paved during my PhD studies. From my perspective, my mathematical background and expertise in computer algebra would assist in leading proposed research on hyperbolic metamaterials.

I would be honored to undertake the proposed research within the ENVIBRO project. I am confident that my academic background and experiences, coupled with the team's expertise, will contribute toward the project's objectives. Thank you for considering my application. I look forward to the possibility of discussing my candidacy in greater detail.

Sincerely,
Afonso Willian Nunes